

The Zhen'gao

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Chinese Daoist Text, Daoism, Chinese Religion, Shangqing (Upper Clarity 上清)

The Zhen'gao 真誥 [Declaration of the Perfected] is an essential work of the Shangqing (上清 Upper Clarity) scriptures that was compiled and collated by an elite Daoist scholar Tao Hongjing 陶弘景 (456-536 CE). The main body of the Zhen'gao is Yang Xi's 楊羲 (330-73 CE) manuscripts of the revelation instructed by a group of Perfected (zhenren 真人), a kind of celestial beings that were conceived as situated in the higher rank than the previous known Transcendent (xianren 仙人) in the Shangqing scriptures. Yang Xi was a well-trained spirit medium who worked for his patrons Xu Mi 許謐 (303-ca.373) and Xu's two sons, Xu Lian 許聯 (328-404) and Xu Hui 許翮 (341-ca.370). During 365-369, Yang Xi received a great number of revelations from his Perfected in Mount Mao. The contents of the revelations are diverse that include descriptions of the celestial world and beings, answers to recipients' questions, instructions on Daoist practices, recipes for drugs and medicine, prophecies for the fates of people, records of dreams, and even the family matters and disputation. Yang Xi's revelation also employs various genres of literature, such as poems, biography, conversation, and marvelous stories, to portray figures, narrate tales, and convey Daoist conceptions. Besides revelation, this work also preserves a few letters between Yang Xi and three Xu, as well as writings of other spirit mediums who preceded Yang Xi. However, these manuscripts were scattered or damaged after Xu Mi's death. The first collection of Yang Xi and three Xus' autography manuscripts was compiled by Gu Huan 顧歡 (425- ca.479 CE) who titled this collection the Zhenji 真迹 [Traces of the Perfected]. The Zhenji has lost. But Tao Hongjing re-compiled, reorganized, and commented on those fragmentary manuscripts based on Gu Huan's version after carefully identifying the authenticity of the calligraphies in the manuscripts. In order to reflect its oral tradition of instruction, Tao Hongjing named this collection the Zhen'gao [Declaration of the Perfected]. The Zhen'gao was divided into seven sections by Tao Hongjing based on the different contents. He also entitled each section with three characters by modeling the format of weft books and the Zhuangzi. The extant version preserved in the Daoist Canon is twenty juan (scroll) along with a preface by Gao Sisun 高似孫 dated 1223. Although Yang Xi claimed through the mouth of his Perfected that the revelation written through his hand in the form of human language was from the celestial realm, these writings quoted a great number of previous Daoist works, classics, contemporary textual sources, and even Buddhist sutra. These quotations provide a rich source for us to explore the intertextuality and the reception of early texts. The Zhen'gao also preserves many historical facts, such as the interpersonal relationship of the Xu family, the connection between the gentry family and the imperial court, and the Daoist genealogy in the Six Dynasties, which offers a special window to investigate the social-historical issues.

Date Range: 365 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Mount Mao (Maoshan 茅山)

Region tags: China, Jiangsu Province, Six Dynasties
China, Mount Mao

Mount Mao 茅山 area of the Six Dynasties in China

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Michel Strickmann, “The Mao-shan Revelations: Taoism and the Aristocracy,” *T’oung-Pao*, 63 (1977) 1-63.
- Source 2: Isabelle Robinet, *Taoist Meditation: The Mao-shan Tradition of Great Purity*, trans. Julian F. Pas and Norman Girardot (Paris: Dervy-Livres, 1979; Albany: State University of New York Press, 1993)
- Source 3: Stephen Bokenkamp, *A Fourth-Century Daoist Family: A New Translation and Study of the Zhen’gao or Declarations of the Perfected* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2021).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://zh.daoinfo.org/index.php?title=真誥&variant=zh-hant>
- Source 2 URL: <https://zh.daoinfo.org/wiki/陶弘景>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=en&res=80529>
- Source 1 Description: Database from Chinese text project.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5d0036/>
- Source 2 Description: Database of Kanripo

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The editor used different colors of ink to indicate the source of the texts, for example: some characters in large size and red color are original manuscripts or transcribed from deities' revelation. Smaller size in red are comments from editor Tao Hongjing. Some characters in large size and purple color are transcribed from the Perfected Three Maos.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: Some of the original paper used by Yang Xi was "white paper from Jingzhou" 荊州白箋.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: unknown

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: unknown

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The first version of Yang Xi's manuscript is called Zhenji真跡(the Traces of the Perfected) which was compiled by Gu Yuan顧歡 (fl. 420–479). Tao Hongjing's Zhen'gao was based on Gu Huan's version.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

Notes: Tao Hongjing criticized Gu Huan's version and pointed out some mistakes caused by Gu Huan's ignorance and carelessness..

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– No

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text includes: Ritual list; Ritual manual; Bibliography

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Daoist body is a multi-spirit dominated body. The basic spirits are three cloud-spirit and seven white-spirit. Besides these, there are numerous spirits in the body, which function through actualiation in the meditation. These spirits monitor and control different parts of the body, at the same time, the body relies on spirits to achieve Transcendent or Perfected. In the Zhen'gao: those who are predestined to be the Perfected will ascend to the celestial realm by leaving their body in various means of release. However, those who are pursuing Transcendent have to nourish their cloud-spirit and refine the white-spirit by following the instructions of Perfection until they can become Transcendent or gain longevity.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Actualizing the spirits that lodge in the different parts of the body in the mind is a critical practice in the Zhen'gao.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: The mind-body dualism does not exist in Daoist concepts.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or

spirit?

– No

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Which spatial location they will go to, "heaven" or "underworld," depends on whether they achieved the Dao successfully and which levels of their ranks.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: It is about a cyclical period of disasters.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: It is not a real debate, just an explanation for the division of human language and the language used by beings from other worlds.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the Zhen'gao, Perfected and Transcendent are all supernatural beings. But some of them used to be human beings who were either predestined to be Perfected or become Transcendent after practicing Daoist methods assiduously.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: They live in the highest heaven. They are called Perfected.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - Yes
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - Yes
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: The female gods have higher status in the heavenly realm compared to the women in real world. They are dominant characters in the practice of revelation.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?
– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?
– Yes

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?
– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?
– Yes

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).
– Yes

Previously human spirits are present
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: not sure.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: Through instructing revelation.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The Perfected (zhenren 真人) is qi-formed celestial beings

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Only spirit medium has the ability to communicate with the Perfected-the main supernatural beings in the Zhen'gao.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: no

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?
– Specify: The pantheon is more like modeled on the court officials. But they did not exactly imitate the structure in the real world.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

Notes: Just the spirit medium, such as Yang Xi can see them and communicated with them.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The dominant supernatural being is zhenren 真人 (Perfected) in the Zhen'gao. This is a new type of qi-formed celestial being who is from the higher heavens, all unknown to previous Daoists. Yang Xi placed the previous-known supernatural being xianren 仙人 (Transcendent) into the lower heaven. Yang Xi's triad of heavens are Grand Clarity, Upper Clarity, and Jade Clarity. The Perfected reside in the middle heaven while the Transcendent reside in the lowest heaven.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– No

- ↳ Human sacrifice?
 - No
- ↳ Sacred objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Daily life objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Gold, money, precious goods.
- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
 - Yes
 - ↳ Food
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred space(s)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred object(s)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Field doesn't know

↳ Incest

– Field doesn't know

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: The Shangqing school highlights the spiritual practice of sex between humans and the Perfected.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Field doesn't know
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
 - Notes: They only care about the conversion of those who are predestined to be the Perfected or whose name has been inscribed in the lu 籙 (register).
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: They also care about family and marriage.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: the punishment is called koala 考罰 (interrogate and punishment)

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: It's done by san guan 三官 (Three Officials)

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: For example, to ensure the ritual is done successfully, they have to retreat or keep precepts. If they do not follow these, they will be punished.

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: Their names will be taken off from the heavenly register.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?
– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Having chances to meet the higher deities.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Messiah was called Li Hong 李弘, the Sage of the Latter Age, who was believed to descend to the world in the year of Ren Chen 壬辰 and saved all Seed People (zhongmin 種民) from the big calamity of this world. He was regarded as the embodiment of Laozi.

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - Yes

- ↳ Alive, identified
 - Yes

- ↳ Coming in this lifetime
 - Yes

- ↳ Coming on a specified date
 - Yes

Notes: The year of Ren Chen 壬辰

- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future
 - No

- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

↳ Coming has already passed

– I don't know

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: Save people from the disaster of this cyclical world.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

Notes: The year of Ten Chen

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The eschatology time is called Yang Nine and Hundred Six 陽九百六. It can be calculated based on the Chinese astronomical calendar. But the exact date of the calamity is not known.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– Yes

↳ Divine judgment event

– Field doesn't know

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

Notes: the new political system is called Grand Peace 太平

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– Yes

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Not sure.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: such as: persistence, filial piety, and righteousness.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Spiritual Elect

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Those who wrote forgery scriptures destroyed the authentic celestial writings.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: To deliver selected people from the big calamity at the end of this world.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Yes

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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